

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 3.1a Outreach programmes and briefings with European institutions and Member States

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Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This report provides a broad overview over ZEP outreach efforts during the first 18 months of the project. ZEP regularly take part in open consultation, finding common positions between its diverse stakeholders from industries, NGOs and research working on CCS and CCU.

ZEP policy and outreach is supported, among others, by its stakeholders taking part in the External Relations Group, which guides ZEP outreach and communication strategy. Moreover, ZEP's position are discuss and define by its stakeholders in the Working Group (WG) Policy and Funding, and its temporary WGs, such as the temporary WG on carbon dioxide removal (CDR).

The following report gives an account of different actions taken by ZEP on different policy files presented by the European Commission over the last 18 months, including the Net-Zero Industry Act, the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy and the Carbon Removal Certification framework. Moreover, ZEP regularly exchanges with representatives of the European Commission, providing input and support to the Commission's ongoing policy work. An overview of these meetings is provided at the end of this report.

Last but not least, ZEP organises and take parts in events both at EU and national level, to share its expertise and position with stakeholders engaged in CCS and CCU.

2 IWG9/ZEP OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

The IWG9 and ZEP actively coordinate their work, including on carbon removals, CCS and CCU, and supply chains. All working group meetings and IWG9 Plenary/ZEP Advisory Councils are effectively coordinated between IWG9 and ZEP to ensure efficiency. European Commission officials attended the 7 IWG9 Plenary/ZEP Advisory Councils that took place in 2022 and 2023, with one last meeting pending on 13 December 2023. Meetings were attended by officials of the European Commission, including DG CLIMA, DG ENER, and DG RTD. Coordinated policy findings were shared and presented to these policymakers throughout these meetings. Other attendees included national government officials working on CCS and CCU. Participants in the ZEP/IWG9 Government Group who are leading national public servants working on CCS and CCU are invited to all IWG9 Plenary/ZEP Advisory Councils. Policy recommendations included in reports and policy papers are directly shared with these officials. Finally, national government officials give a presentation at each IWG9 Plenary/ZEP Advisory Council. The last presentation was made by French public officials in September 2023 on France's draft CCS strategy. This allows direct feedback and engagement regarding policy being developed.

3 NET-ZERO INDUSTRY ACT

3.1 ZEP's Position on NZIA proposal

In April 2023, following the adoption of the Net-Zero Industry Act, ZEP wrote two position papers welcoming the introduction of a CO₂ storage target and inquiring the European Commission to provide more clarity on certain points. The following points were raised in a position letter:

- Will there still be a specific 50 million tonnes per annum objective for the EU also after the inclusion of the regulation into the EEA agreement?
- How to guarantee that the most cost-efficient storage solutions are developed first?
- How will Member States that do not allow CO₂ storage be treated?
- How storage in aquifers will be taken into account?
- How oil and gas licence holders in these countries will be ensured access to storage acreage across the EU?
- What is the precise methodology for the “pro-rata” calculation mentioned under Article 18?

The position paper reacting to and welcoming the NZIA can be read [here](#) and the longer position paper requiring more clarity can be read [here](#).

3.2 Recommendation on NZIA proposal

Within the WG Policy & Funding, ZEP drafted amendments to the NZIA proposal as part of an outreach effort with the European Parliament ITRE Committee. Some of the amendments raised the following points:

- The need to include not only CO₂ storage and manufacturing of technologies but all parts of the value chain, including also the capture and transport of CO₂, in the Act's definition of strategic net-zero projects, description of planning, the maximum 18 months permitting process, etc.
- That the defined maximum 18 months for permitting must include all procedural steps, starting from the initial submission of the draft permit-granting application.
- The need to also include offshore and spatial planning in seaports regarding CO₂ storage infrastructure.
- The importance of strengthening the support for CCS and CCU research and innovation (R&I).
- That capacity building at the level of competent authorities will need to include all parts of the CCS value chain, also capture and transport.
- The importance of taking into account the UK for CO₂ storage.

3.3 Open letter on Article 18

In July 2023, ZEP, Bellona Europe and the International Association of Oil & Gas (IOGP) jointly drafted an open letter urging policymakers and decision-makers to work toward an implementable and pragmatic Net Zero Industry Act 18. The letter was jointly signed by ZEP, Bellona Europe, IOGP, the Clean Air Task Force, SINTEF and the CCSA. The content of the letter can be read [here](#).

The letter was sent to key actors in the European Parliament, the Council and the European Commission.

3.4 Outreach to Members of European Parliament

In the build-up of the EP ITRE Committee position on the NZIA, and upon request of members of the External Relations Group, ZEP formulated a position in the WG Policy & Funding requesting MEPs to take into considerations the following points:

- ZEP strongly supports an objective of at least 50 million tonnes of CO₂ of annual injection capacity by 2030 for storage in the EU under Article 16 of the Net Zero Industry Act. ZEP considers that a 2030 EU injection capacity objective of 50 million tonnes per annum is a minimum requirement that should be kept in the Act.
- ZEP would recommend referring to an injection capacity objective that covers the EU, in line with ZEP's position. Furthermore, it is crucial that the EU market is supplemented by a Europe-wide market for CO₂ storage that covers the European Economic Area (EEA) and the UK.
- ZEP would like to highlight that the term 'unavoidable industrial process emissions' could create confusion. Technical feasibility is not the only criterion to determine the most appropriate decarbonisation solution. The possibility to deploy CCS at scale this decade and its economic feasibility are also crucial to determine its role for industrial decarbonisation. The focus should be on hard-to-abate industrial sectors.

ZEP's position, as well as the above mentioned open-letter and NZIA position were sent to the rapport and shadow rapporteurs for the NZIA on 23 October 2023.

3.5 Outreach to Member States

The ZEP Secretariat reached out to representatives of Member States Permanent Representations, in particular the Netherlands, Denmark and Romania, to gain a better understanding of their position on the NZIA.

4 INDUSTRIAL CARBON MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

4.1 Call for feedback

In August 2023, ZEP responded to the European Commission's call for feedback to the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy. In summary, the feedback raised the following considerations.

- EU support for CCS and CCU: ZEP advocates for focused support for CCS/CCU technologies, with support for deployment based on full Life Cycle Assessments.
- Supporting industrial carbon removals: ZEP welcomes the potential integration of industrial carbon removals into the EU ETS and looks forward to collaborating with the EC on the various market design options while ensuring informed decision-making.
- Barriers for CCS development: We stress the importance of a value chain approach to accelerate CO₂ capture, transport infrastructure, and storage capacity deployment.

- CO₂ transport infrastructure: ZEP calls for the establishment of a regulatory framework for CO₂ transport to establish a clear regulatory basis for project and cross-border cooperation.
- Common CO₂ Standards: ZEP urges EU legislators to play a pivotal role in setting common CO₂ standards and recalls the work of the expert group on CO₂ specifications.
- Mapping CO₂ storage across Europe: ZEP urges that CO₂ storage capacity across Europe is mapped and continuously updated through the setup of a CO₂ Storage Atlas.
- Updated NECPs: ZEP highlights the importance of aligning the ICM strategy with National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) to promote CCS and CCU projects at national and regional levels.
- Project Network: ZEP wants to highlight its new Projects Network designed to foster EU/EEA-wide project-to-project information sharing.

The feedback can be read in its entirety [here](#).

4.2 DG ENER workshop on feedback

ZEP took part in the workshop on the ICM strategy feedback on October 6.

4.3 CCUS Forum

ZEP co-chairs the CCUS Forum working group on CO₂ infrastructure. See deliverable 2.5 for more information.

5 EU ETS REVISION

In August 2023, ZEP responded to the European Commission call for feedback “EU ETS – update of the rules for monitoring and reporting emissions” which closed on 23 August. ZEP responded to the feedback drawing from a [previous position](#), and the support of members of the WG Policy & Funding. ZEP’s feedback can be read [here](#).

6 INNOVATION FUND

In March 2023, ZEP responded to the European Commission DG CLIMA’s open consultation on the future operation of the Innovation Fund. ZEP’s response highlights the need for simplification, frontloading, and project de-risking. The response can be read [here](#).

7 EU CERTIFICATION FRAMEWORK FOR CARBON REMOVALS

7.1 Call for evidence

In March 2022, ZEP responded to the European Commission’s call for evidence on the certification of carbon removals. ZEP’s response can be read [here](#).

7.2 Call for feedback

In March 2023, ZEP responded to the call for feedback on the Certification of carbon removals. ZEP's response raised a couple considerations to be considered in the framework. The response can be read [here](#).

7.3 Carbon removals expert group

ZEP takes part in the European Commission's carbon removals expert group, supporting and advising the EC with its methodology. ZEP is represented by Kristin Jordal, chief scientist at SINTEF.

8 EU 2040 CLIMATE TARGET

In June 2023, ZEP responded to the European Commission's call for input on the EU 2040 climate target. ZEP WG on policy and funding the temporary WG on CDR prepared a response to the consultation. The response can be read [here](#).

9 CO2 STORAGE DIRECTIVE

ZEP responded to the DNV and the European Commission call for input: industrial removal certification methodologies which closed on 15 September 2023. ZEP defined its response in the temporary WG on CDR with support from the CCSA. The response can be read [here](#).

10 TEN-E REVISION

In March 2023, ZEP responded to the consultation on the list of candidate PCIs in the CO2 networks, advocating for strong need for European open access, cross-border CO2 infrastructure. The response can be read [here](#).

11 FUTURE OF HORIZON R&I

In February 2023, ZEP responded to the European Commission DG RTD public consultation on the "Past, present and future of the European research and innovation programmes 2014-2027. ZEP responded to the consultation together with EERA and supported by the IWG9. The response, that is based on previous ZEP/EERA/IWG9 documents, highlights the R&I priorities for upcoming work programmes, the importance of collaboration/coordination and knowledge sharing, and the need to streamline calls and evaluation processes. The response can be read [here](#).

12 MEETINGS WITH EUROPEAN COMMISSION

12.1 June 2023 outreach campaign with European Commission

ZEP constituents elected a new Chair in January 2023. As part of an effort outreach effort, meetings were set-up between key officials of the European Commission, the ZEP Chair and ZEP Secretariat during the summer starting June 2023. Below is an overview and description of the meetings.

Meeting with Chris Bolesta and Johanna Fiksdahl, DG ENER (13 June) – Participants from ZEP: Eve Tamme and Per-Olof Granström

The ongoing ZEP work, the new Network Project, and the further development of ZEP was presented and discussed. The participants discussed the upcoming CCUS Forum plenary in Denmark on 27-28 November, the ongoing work, the draft programme and the possibility for the new ZEP Network Projects to have a session on day two of the plenary. Chris noted support for the new ZEP Network Projects, hinted that this could be a good solution for the CCUS Forum work on an Industrial Partnership, and noted that other projects working on knowledge sharing would not be an alternative.

It was a good meeting with good support for ZEP and its work.

Meeting with Ruud Kempener, member of Commissioner Simson's cabinet (20 June) – Participants from ZEP: Eve Tamme and Per-Olof Granström

The work of ZEP, the groups noting the Governments Group and the ongoing work and upcoming reports. The further development of ZEP and the new Network Project was also presented. The participants discussed the importance of European CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure, the NZIA process and the need to include the whole CCS value chain in the new regulation, and how to go about the possible inclusion of CCU in the EU ETS.

The participants discussed the upcoming strategy and the next step after the strategy has been published this autumn. Ruud highlighted the interest to see an EU ministerial meeting in January or February next year to follow up on the strategy and the draft National Energy and Climate Plans. He asked for support to make this happen.

Ruud noted interest in the ongoing ZEP work on CO₂ transport by ship and the expert group work on CO₂ transport specifications. These will be shared with him as soon as they are ready.

This was a very good meeting and Ruud asked for a follow-up meeting after the summer.

Meeting with Maria Velkova and Daniel Kitscha, DG CLIMA (21 June) – Participants from ZEP: Eve Tamme, Jonas Helseth, Per-Olof Granström and Ana Faria

Participants discussed the expected evolution of the Innovation Fund (IF) and the foreseen budget for CCS and CCU, considering the recently proposed Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP). DG CLIMA mentioned that demand for IF funding could be expected to increase given the introduction of new sectors in the programme which already experiences substantial oversubscription. National funding instruments were mentioned as a key complement to support projects. Regarding STEP, DG CLIMA mentioned that a swift decision process could be expected.

Participants to the meeting also discussed the Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA), focusing on the ongoing discussion at the Council level and the concerns of some Member States. DG CLIMA noted it would be important for ZEP, as a stakeholder representative, to demonstrate support for the NZIA and its Article 18, and to continue raising awareness on the benefits of CCS, particularly outside the regular circles.

ZEP presented its plans to develop a New Network Projects in order to support project development through knowledge sharing.

Meeting with Catharina Sikow-Magny DG ENER (11 September) – Participants from ZEP: Eve Tamme, Joop Hazenberg

Participants discussed the upcoming CCUS Forum in Aalborg, where the upcoming International Carbon Management Strategy would ideally be presented. This strategy would directly feed into the next EC work programme. It was also informed that the IEA will launch its own report at the Forum, focusing on CCUS business models.

Participants discussed the CCS strategy and the distribution of work between the different DGs, with ENER working on transport of CO₂ and CLIMA working on storage.

ZEP presented its new Projects Network and discussed the opportunity of an ENER officer co-chairing the Network.

12.2 Meeting with DG TRADE

Upon invitation, ZEP met with representatives from DG TRADE E3 to present the state-of-play of CCS, and what will be needed in terms of securing the supply chain. The meeting was attended from the ZEP Secretariat by Per-Olof Granstrom, Joop Hazenberg and Kristin Heidebroek.

12.3 Advisory Council meetings

European Commission representatives are regularly invited to speak during ZEP Advisory Council meetings to update stakeholders about the status of policy files and funding opportunities.

13 EVENTS & SPEAKING ENGAGEMENTS

13.1 Webinar – learning from experience in geological CO₂ storage

On 18 July, the Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) held an online seminar titled Learning from experience in geological CO₂ storage. The event showcased the latest report by ZEP on geological CO₂ storage ([link](#)), released in the context of the European Commission's upcoming update of the guidance documents that are linked to the Directive on the geological storage of CO₂.

The event was chaired by Per-Olof Granström and featured authors and experts: Filip Neele – Co-Chair of ZEP's Network Technology, Maria Velkova – Deputy Head of Unit at DG CLIMA, Gloria Thurschmid – EBN, Thomas Le Guéan – BRGM, as well as Toby Lockwood – Clean Air Task Force.

After a presentation of the report, which suggests key amendments to the guidance documents, participants engaged in a discussion and Q&A session. It was an excellent opportunity to highlight the ongoing call for tenders by DG CLIMA to support the update of the guidance documents, available [here](#).

The experts highlighted the importance for competent authorities to engage early on in the process with storage projects – managing expectations among stakeholders and providing clarity about the technical details and functional requirements of a successful permit application. These elements are among many other required steps to accelerate the learning curve for fast deployment, at a time when CO₂ storage is considered to be a bottleneck in Europe. This revision of the guidance documents will therefore be crucial for successful CCS-based climate mitigation at large-scale.

13.2 Conference – Net Zero Within Reach

In April 2023, the Net Zero Within Reach conference, organized by the Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) and the Carbon Capture and Storage Association (CCSA), brought together 200 participants to discuss the crucial role of CCS and CCU in achieving net-zero targets in Europe. Keynote speakers included Ruud Kempener from the European Commission and ZEP Chair Eve Tamme. Panel sessions covered EU strategies, investment, CO₂ transport, removal, and public acceptance.

The conference underscored the significance of CCS and CCU technologies in reaching net-zero goals, emphasizing policies, collaboration, and a whole-value chain approach for success.

Building on its success, the event is planned to become an annual knowledge-sharing platform for CCS and CCU developments in Europe.

13.3 EUSEW – Climate neutral Europe: Safeguarding jobs and industrial competitiveness

ZEP organised a policy session dedicated to the skills and training needed for CCS and the role of CCS in the energy transition at the 2023 EU Sustainable Energy Week. The session was moderated by ZEP and included speakers from industry, projects, trade unions, and the European Commission. The panellists emphasised the crucial role of CCS for the industry and that existing skills can be used for CCS deployment ([link to the session details and recording in the online programme](#)).

13.4 EU Industry Days – Decarbonising with carbon capture and storage: a pathway to green transformation and industrial competitiveness

ZEP co-hosted a stakeholder session during the EU Industry Days organised in Malaga. The panel included representatives from NGOs and the industries. Speakers emphasised the need for supportive EU and national regulatory frameworks in order to support industries access to CO₂ storage. A summary of the session can be read [here](#).

13.5 Speaking engagements

ZEP Chair and Secretary General are regularly invited to speak and/or moderate at different events on CCS and CCU. Below is a short overview of some of these speaking engagements.

- October 2022 - CCUS Conference (CCSA) in London
- February 2023 - CLIMIT Conference in Oslo
- June 2023 – CCS4CEE Conference in Brussels
- June 2023 – 2023 Europe Forum on CCS (GCSSI) in Brussels
- June 2023 – Carbon Capture Summit in Amsterdam
- September 2023 – CONSECUS Webinar online
- October 2023 – Springboard to Net Zero CCUS Conference (CCSA) in London
- October 2023 – European Gas Tech Conference (Eurogas) online